

FOSTERING INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOR IN NEW PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

Khawaja Zeeshan Waheed^{*1}, Muhammad Ishfaq Khan²

^{*1,2}Management Sciences Department, Capital University of Science & Technology, Islamabad, Pakistan

¹saigol@gmail.com, ²ishfaq@cust.edu.pk

¹<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-6382-5524>, ²<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1526-9032>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17490189>

Keywords

Innovative work behavior, New product development, Projects, Innovation

Article History

Received: 12 September 2025

Accepted: 18 October 2025

Published: 31 October 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Khawaja Zeeshan Waheed

Abstract

In fast changing and competitive IT market innovative work behavior (IWB) has become essential by organizations in an effort to ensure success, specially in new product development (NPD) projects. This research provides a systematic literature review to demonstrate how firms can facilitate IWB in NPD initiatives, providing a holistic approach for innovation driven projects. Using PRISMA guidelines, we reviewed empirical and conceptual research published over the last twenty-five years with a focus on research from organizational behavior, leadership and HRM areas in NPD projects. A thematic synthesis was carried out grouping four key categories i.e. (1) antecedents of IWB, (2) mediating and moderating mechanisms, (3) outcomes and (4) barriers associated with cultural, structural and contextual constraints. Results highlighted the importance of different leadership styles, HR practices and varying climates as key enablers of IWB in NPD projects. Also, leading from these studies, research gaps that need to be investigated were also brought forward for future studies. By incorporating divergent results, the review contributes to theory on IWB in NPD and offers practical recommendations to project managers, innovation leaders and policy makers on how to create work environments in which creativity and idea implementation are fostered. Future research should include multi-stage, multi-level studies, investigate leadership styles and vary methods to reflect the changing nature of IWB in NPD settings. These insights can be used in the allocation of resources and training programs to maintain long-term innovation capabilities.

INTRODUCTION

Global IT and NPD market is marked by accelerating technological changes and dynamic conditions highlighting innovation as an essential tool for sustaining competitive advantage. In order to remain effective organizations must foster innovative work behavior (IWB) within their workforce to remain agile and effective (Braun & Follert, 2024). Central to this market dynamism, IWB is an intentional process involving the generation, promotion and implementation of novel ideas within their role, team

or organization in order to improve their performance and competitiveness (Khalili & Arya, 2023; Yasir et al., 2022) and unlike creativity, which emphasizes only on idea generation, IWB covers the whole innovation cycle from conception through execution, thus becoming indispensable in the face of uncertainty in a turbulent environment, indicating organizational adaptability. New product development (NPD) projects, which are highlighted by high uncertainty, cross-disciplinary collaboration and knowledge

intensiveness, are especially subjected to the use IWB by their employees who need to break entrenched routines, exchange experiences and translate creative thoughts into market-ready innovations (Handiman & Adam, 2024). In such contexts, IWB is not an option but imperative in helping the product development processes keep up with the changing demands in the markets. The research on IWB in NPD context still appears insufficient, while the antecedents of IWB in NPD context are identified mainly in the categories of leadership styles like transformational, empowering, entrepreneurial and servant leadership (Jain & Sharma, 2025), human resource practices like training, rewards, autonomy and organizational climate like trust, psychological safety (Nguyen & Tran, 2023). However, findings are often isolated and thus have no integrative frameworks. Mediating mechanisms such as intrinsic motivation, knowledge sharing and psychological empowerment have been examined but rarely been synthesized in project specific contexts (Yang & Park, 2023). Similarly, evidence on outcomes that range from enhanced performance and innovation of individual projects and organizations to employee well-being, is also inconsistent, particularly in cross-cultural and digitally mediated environments (Liu et al., 2023). These gaps highlight the importance of a systematic literature review (SLR) that consolidates and synthesizes the existing findings. Guided by PRISMA protocols our review analyses empirical and conceptual works published between 2000 and 2025. Based on our four guiding research questions :-

RQ1. What are the key antecedents of IWB in NPD project contexts?

RQ2. What are the mediating and moderating mechanisms that can nurture and take advantage of IWB?

RQ3. What obstacles impede IWB in the success of NPD projects?

RQ4. What are the outcomes associated with IWB in NPD projects?

More systematically responding to these questions, the review provides a framework that unifies the scattered evidences of the IWB in NPD projects to develop theory and provide practical guidance to managers, project leaders and policy makers on how

to stimulate the necessary innovative work behavior for long-term organizational performance.

2. Methodology

Systematic literature reviews (SLRs) are widely recognized as rigorous, transparent and replicable approaches to synthesizing evidence, ensuring maximum coverage of relevant studies while minimizing bias (Kraus et al., 2022; Page et al., 2021) in management and organizational research. The PRISMA framework has gained prominence for improving methodological rigor, transparency and reproducibility (Booth et al., 2023), and thus, in this review the authors have followed PRISMA guidelines to ensure comprehensiveness and credibility.

2.1. Search Strategy

The search strategy was designed to capture empirical and conceptual studies published between 2000 and 2025, reflecting the period in which research on innovative work behavior (IWB) gained significant momentum; to ensure both recency and depth. Searches were conducted across Scopus, Web of Science, PsycINFO and Google Scholar, as these databases offer extensive coverage of organizational behavior, project management and innovation-related literature (Donthu et al., 2021) and search strings were refined using Boolean operators and relevant keywords to maximize inclusivity, such as:

- “innovative work behavior” AND “new product development”,
- “employee innovation” AND “project management”,
- “IWB” AND “innovation projects”, and
- “fostering innovation” AND “work behavior”,

thereby ensuring retrieval of studies capturing both IWB and related constructs (e.g., pro-innovation behavior, creativity implementation) in contexts such as NPD, R&D projects and innovation teams. Inclusion criteria were established to ensure relevance and methodological rigor, while exclusion criteria ruled out irrelevant studies (see Table 1).

Table 1. Inclusion / Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Studies explicitly addressing IWB or related constructs	Studies focusing only on creativity without linking to IWB processes
Empirical or conceptual works situated in NPD or innovation project contexts	Non-peer-reviewed sources (e.g., practitioner reports, book chapters)
Peer-reviewed journal articles or peer-reviewed conference papers	Studies outside organizational or project-based settings
Publications between 2000–2025 in English	

2.2. Selection and Screening Process

The selection procedure followed three stages:

- **Preliminary search** database queries produced an initial pool of records.
- **Title and abstract screening** duplicates and clearly irrelevant studies were removed.

- **Full-text review** remaining articles were assessed for alignment with the review’s scope, leading to the final set of included studies. The selection process is summarized in a **PRISMA flow diagram** (See Figure 1), illustrating the number of records identified, screened, excluded, and retained.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram

2.3. Data Extraction and Synthesis

For each included study, data were extracted on the basis of authors, year of publication, context, research design, sample, key findings and thematic contributions. A **thematic synthesis** approach (Hoon, 2013) was applied and coding of findings into four domains (antecedents, mediators/moderators, outcomes and barriers) was done. This facilitated integrative comparisons across studies and revealed gaps and inconsistencies.

2.4. Quality Assessment

The rigor of included studies was assessed against methodological quality criteria, including clarity of IWB conceptualization, appropriateness of research design and validity of findings (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006). This ensured conclusions based on credible evidences.

3. Results and Findings

3.1 Antecedents of Innovative Work Behavior in NPD Projects Antecedents of Innovative Work Behavior (IWB) are multidimensional and consist of individual, interpersonal and organizational factors that interact to shape employees' actions toward innovative activities. Individual elements (psychological empowerment, self-efficacy, and personality traits) were continuously associated with higher levels of IWB since these elements helped develop employees' confidence and motivation to generate and implement new ideas (Morales & Pacheco, 2024). Interpersonal relations such as leadership styles like transformational and ethical leadership lead to the creation of psychological safety and trust which also lead to creativity and innovation within the teams (Ajrurrahman & Pusparini, 2024; Muchiri et al., 2020). Organizational antecedents

including support climate, HRM practices, knowledge sharing mechanisms and innovation oriented culture are structural enablers of IWB and helped to create an environment that is conducive to experimentation and learning (Jishnu & Hareendrakumar, 2024; Almeida & Moreira, 2022). Systematic reviews have grouped these antecedents into domains of institutional and employee-related antecedents and emphasized the integrative characteristic of innovation drivers (Alfy & Naithani,

2021). Contextual factors like work autonomy, teamwork and the management of different employees also affect the extent to which innovative behaviors are practiced in organizations (Manalo et al., 2025; Khan, 2021). These findings also support the view that IWB is a synergistic interaction of the combination of individual capabilities, supportive leadership and organizational systems. Top 10 relevant and latest antecedents of IWB are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Latest Antecedents of IWB in NPD Projects

	Antecedent	Description	Authors
1	Transformational Leadership	Inspires and motivates employees through vision, individualized consideration and intellectual stimulation, fostering creativity and innovation.	Mursaleen et al. (2024); Mozie & Mahadi (2024); Muchiri et al. (2020)
2	Entrepreneurial Leadership	Emphasizes opportunity recognition, exhibits pro-activeness, risk-taking, adaptability, drives IWB by empowering employees to champion and implement novel ideas in dynamic environments.	Chakim et al. (2024); Mozie & Mahadi (2024); Ebrahim et al. (2023)
3	Organizational Climate / Supportive Culture	A positive, open and collaborative climate that encourages experimentation and psychological safety enhances employees' innovative behaviors.	Al-Qahtani (2025); Salsabila & Mansyur (2024); Khan (2021)
4	Psychological Empowerment	Feelings of competence, meaning, and autonomy motivate employees to engage in and sustain innovation.	Ajrurrahman & Pusparini (2024); Ebrahim et al. (2023); Jain (2015)
5	Knowledge Sharing and Collaboration	Social exchange and team collaboration mediate the relationship between leadership and IWB.	Jishnu & Hareendrakumar (2024); Ajrurrahman & Pusparini (2024)
6	HRM Practices (Training, Rewards, Work-Life Balance)	Strategic HR systems influence IWB differently i.e. training and diversity enhance innovation, while rewards yield mixed effects.	Manalo et al. (2025); Jishnu & Hareendrakumar (2024)
7	Ethical Leadership / Psychological Safety	Ethical and fair leaders create trust and psychological safety, encouraging idea generation and implementation.	Mozie & Mahadi (2024); Ajrurrahman & Pusparini (2024)
8	Personality Traits & Self-Efficacy	Self-efficacy, achievement motivation and proactivity predict persistent innovation.	Morales & Pacheco (2024); Liang et al. (2022)
9	Organizational Justice / Fairness Perceptions	Fair and transparent systems enhance trust and commitment to innovative behaviors.	Ajrurrahman & Pusparini (2024); Muchiri et al. (2020)
10	Innovation-Oriented Leadership Climate	Leaders who encourage risk-taking and creativity create a climate that nurtures IWB.	Delhi (2024); Ebrahim et al. (2023); AlEssa & Durugbo (2021)

3.2. Mediating and Moderating Mechanisms of IWB

3.2.1. Mediating Mechanisms

Mediators are necessary in showing the processes by which individual, organizational and leadership antecedents are translated into Innovative Work Behavior (IWB) and the power they exert is constantly indicated in empirical research. Psychological empowerment enhances employees' intrinsic motivation, autonomy and confidence in shaping innovative outcomes. This provides supportive climates and leadership practices and are turned into concrete innovative actions (Ebrahim et al., 2023). This pathway is further strengthened by implicit self-efficacy, as it generates the belief and resilience needed to explore new concepts that are more clear when coupled with transformational or entrepreneurial leadership (Morales & Pacheco, 2024; Liang et al, 2022). Employee's creativity as a proximal behavioral mediator is the relationship between psychological states and empowerment to the new idea generation and idea implementation (Salsabila & Mansyur, 2024). Moreover, agility of

employees, including elements such as adaptability, a learning orientation and reactivity to changes has become a key mediator in dynamic circumstances, especially in IT and innovation driven projects (Chakim et al., 2024). Psychological capital, which includes optimism, resilience and hope is a multidimensional mediating variable in the relationship between leadership and innovation (Ajrurrahman & Pusparini, 2024). Knowledge sharing and collaboration are social mediators which translated the employee creativity into collective innovative output (Jishnu & Hareendrakumar, 2024). Together with the cognitive, emotional and social mechanisms described in various other theories like SCT, SDT, etc and these mediators shed light on a complex interplay that may lead to a sustained innovative performance for organizations that support IWB by enablers facilitated through open sourcing. Top 10 relevant and latest Mediators of IWB are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Mediators of Innovative Work Behavior (IWB)

	Mediator	Description	Authors
1	Psychological Empowerment	A sense of competence, autonomy, and meaning that motivates employees to engage in innovative acts.	Ebrahim et al. (2023); Jain (2015)
2	Self-Efficacy	Belief in one's capability to execute creative tasks and persist through challenges in innovation.	Morales & Pacheco (2024); Liang et al. (2022)
3	Employee Creativity	The ability to generate and refine novel ideas that mediate the effect of climate and empowerment on IWB.	Salsabila & Mansyur (2024); Jain (2015)
4	Employee Agility	Adaptability, learning orientation, and responsiveness that convert leadership vision into innovative performance.	Chakim et al. (2024); Mozie & Mahadi (2024)
5	Knowledge Sharing	Exchange of knowledge among team members that fosters idea development and collaborative innovation.	Jishnu & Hareendrakumar (2024); Ajrurrahman & Pusparini (2024)
6	Psychological Safety	A climate of trust and openness that encourages risk-taking and experimentation without fear of negative consequences.	Mozie & Mahadi (2024); Ajrurrahman & Pusparini (2024)
7	Psychological Capital	Positive psychological resources like hope, optimism and resilience that sustain innovative engagement.	Ajrurrahman & Pusparini (2024); Jain (2015)

8	Work Engagement	High levels of energy, dedication, and absorption that channel empowerment into innovative effort.	Manalo et al. (2025); Mursaleen et al. (2024)
9	Organizational Support	Perceived recognition and backing from the organization that strengthens the motivation to innovate.	Jishnu & Hareendrakumar (2024); AlEssa & Durugbo (2021)
10	Job Satisfaction / Commitment	Emotional attachment and satisfaction that reinforce employees' willingness to invest in innovation.	Salsabila & Mansyur, (2024); Dayanti (2024).

3.2.2. Moderating Mechanisms

Moderators clarify under what conditions the antecedents of IWB will impact IWB. How these affect the direction or strength of relation between leadership, individual and organizational factors and employees' innovation engagement. Indeed, empowering climate is one of the most salient moderators as it supports autonomy, participative decision-making and psychological safety and therefore enhances the effects of transformational and entrepreneurial leadership on IWB (Al-Qahtani, 2025; Mozie & Mahadi, 2024). It enhances motivational pathways between leadership and innovation, by assuring employees' trustworthiness and support. Likewise, work strengthens the impact of psychological empowerment and self-efficacy on IWB. Employees who appear highly involved in their roles are those who are mostly likely to convert

creative potential into creative outcomes (Dayanti, 2024). Other works emphasize organizational justice and fairness in leadership as moderators to strengthen the relationship between ethical leadership and IWB through reinforcing the normative influence (Ajrurrahman & Pusparini, 2024; Muchiri, et al., 2020). Personal innovativeness and proactive personality are also found to moderate the effects of perceived work environment and leadership on innovation, reflecting individual differences of openness to change (Hai & et al., 2024; Morales & Pachecoco, 2024). This moderator perspective suggests the presence of boundary conditions including climate, positive employee perceptions and perceptions of organizational justice lead to optimal innovative behavior in organizational environments. Top 10 relevant and latest Moderators of IWB are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Moderators of Innovative Work Behavior (IWB) Relationships

	Moderator	Description	Authors
1	Empowering Climate	A supportive environment that promotes autonomy, participation, and trust, strengthens the leadership-IWB relationship.	Al-Qahtani (2025); Mozie & Mahadi (2024)
2	Work Involvement	Degree of psychological identification with one's work that magnifies the effects of empowerment and self-efficacy on IWB.	Waheed & Khan (2025); Dayanti (2024)
3	Organizational Justice	Perceived fairness in policies and leadership that moderates ethical leadership's impact on innovation.	Ajrurrahman & Pusparini (2024); Muchiri et al. (2020)
4	Personal Innovativeness	Individual openness to experimentation that strengthens the influence of work environment on IWB.	Hai et al. (2024)

5	Proactive Personality	A forward-looking, change-oriented disposition that enhances leadership’s effects on innovation.	Morales & Pacheco (2024); Mozié & Mahadi (2024)
6	Digital Leadership	Leadership leveraging technology to augment creativity and IWB	Yuwanda et al. (2023)
7	Knowledge Sharing Culture	A collaborative atmosphere that enhances HR practices’ and empowerment’s effects on IWB.	Jishnu & Hareendrakumar (2024)
8	Innovation-Oriented Organizational Climate	The extent to which the organization values and rewards innovation; strengthens motivation–IWB link.	Delhi (2024) ; AlEssa & Durugbo (2021)
9	Leadership Fairness / Ethical Context	The perception of fairness and moral conduct moderating leadership and creativity relationships.	Ajrurrahman & Pusparini (2024); Muchiri et al. (2020)
10	Psychological Safety	A climate where employees feel safe to express ideas and take risks; enhances empowerment’s effect on IWB.	Mozié & Mahadi (2024); Ebrahim et al. (2023)

3.3. Outcomes of IWB in NPD Projects

Innovative Work Behavior (IWB) results in a number of positive outcomes at the individual, and organizational level and thus represents a key determinant of future success and sustainability. On the individual side IWB increases employee performance, job satisfaction, and learning orientation by promoting creative problem-solving participation using continuous improvement (Dayanti, 2024; Ebrahim et al., 2023). Workers who continuously generate and develop new ideas with high levels of motivation, flexibility and the ability to learn are willing to develop themselves professionally and personally (Morales & Pacheco, 2024). At the organizational level, IWB as a whole fosters a collective approach to innovation capacity, teamwork and ability to compete due to the shared creativity

and collaboration and ability to react to environmental changes (Manalo et al., 2025; Ajrurrahman & Pusparini, 2024). When it comes to organizations, IWB has been found to not only contribute to better financial performance, profitability and sustainability but also to help organizations adapt to technological and market changes (Al-Qahtani, 2025; Khan, 2021). IWB contributes to organizational learning and knowledge sharing, which are dynamic capabilities for organizations to be innovating quickly and remaining relevant in times of uncertainty (Sjahruddin et al., 2024). After all, IWB acts as a behavioral tool for creativity led intrusion converting individual creativity into growth, transformation and long-term critical success. Top 10 relevant and latest outcomes of IWB are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Outcomes of Innovative Work Behavior (IWB)

	Outcome	Level	Description	Author
1	Employee Performance	Individual	IWB enhances task efficiency, creativity, and quality of output through innovative idea application.	Mozié & Mahadi (2024); Ebrahim et al. (2023)
2	Job Satisfaction	Individual	Engaging in innovative tasks increases intrinsic motivation and fulfillment.	Dayanti (2024); Muchiri et al. (2020)

3	Learning and Skill Development	Individual	Continuous idea generation promotes learning agility and self-improvement.	Morales & Pacheco (2024); Jishnu & Hareendrakumar (2024)
4	Employee Engagement and Commitment	Individual	Innovative employees show higher involvement, dedication, and organizational loyalty.	Al-Qahtani (2025); Sjahruddin et al. (2024)
5	Team Collaboration and Effectiveness	Team	IWB promotes knowledge sharing, communication and synergy within teams.	Manalo et al. (2025); Ajrurrahman & Pusparini (2024);
6	Organizational Innovation Capability	Organizational	Collective innovative behavior builds a firm's capacity to adapt and innovate continuously.	Almeida & Moreira (2022); Manalo et al. (2025)
7	Business Performance and Growth	Organizational	IWB contributes to profitability, productivity, and competitive positioning.	Al-Qahtani (2025); Sjahruddin et al. (2024)
8	Organizational Sustainability	Organizational	Innovation behavior ensures adaptability to technological and environmental change.	Chakim et al. (2024); Khan (2021)
9	Knowledge Creation and Sharing	Team	Innovative employees exchange and apply ideas, enhancing organizational learning.	Jishnu & Hareendrakumar (2024); Ajrurrahman & Pusparini (2024)
10	Organizational Adaptability and Resilience	Organizational	IWB drives firms' responsiveness to crises and fosters long-term stability.	Chakim et al. (2024); Mozie & Mahadi (2024)

3.4. Barriers and Challenges to IWB in NPD Projects

There are many organizational factors and challenges to Innovative Work Behavior (IWB) that cause organization-based employees to perform low in generating, performing and implementing new ideas. As reviewed in literature in this study, there are a number of individual, organizational and contextual barriers to innovation potential. At the individual level, employees' fear of failure, low self-efficacy and resistance to change decrease their desire to take creative risks or make suggestions for new ways of doing things (Morales & Pacheco, 2024; Liang et al., 2022). At the organizational level, the organizational structures that discourage idea flow and experimentation include ineffective management support, hierarchical organization structure and the structures that promote bureaucratic decision-making (Muchiri et al., 2020; Al-Qahtani, 2025). Besides, lack

of resources, work-load and absence of clarity on innovation policies provide a context in which employees focus on repetitive efficiency rather than creativity (Ebrahim et al., 2023). The weak empowering climate and low psychological safety, which discourages collaboration and communication, are a cultural point of concern (Mozie & Mahadi, 2024). These difficulties are worsened by external factors like technological limitations and uncertainty in the environment, which reduce organizational flexibility and employee confidence in the implementation of new ideas (Chakim et al., 2024). These barriers indicate that IWB not only needs individual creativity but supportive mechanisms in terms of leadership styles and organizational culture to conquer fear, restrictions of resources and rigidity of organizations. Top 10 barriers identified in recent studies are shown in table 6.

Table 6. Barriers to IWB in NPD Projects

	Barrier / Challenges	Level	Brief Description	Authors
1	Fear of Failure and Risk Aversion	Individual	Employees hesitate to take creative risks due to fear of mistakes and negative evaluation.	Morales & Pacheco (2024); Liang et al. (2022)
2	Low Self-Efficacy	Individual	Lack of confidence in one's ability to innovate hinders engagement in creative problem-solving.	Morales & Pacheco (2024); Jain (2015)
3	Resistance to Change	Individual	Employees' preference for familiar routines limits adaptability and innovation adoption.	Al-Qahtani (2025); Muchiri et al. (2020)
4	Rigid Hierarchies and Bureaucracy	Organizational	Centralized structures restrict autonomy, slowing decision-making and idea implementation.	Mozie & Mahadi (2024); Ebrahim et al. (2023)
5	Lack of Managerial and Leadership Support	Organizational	Absence of encouragement or recognition from leaders reduces motivation to innovate.	Al-Qahtani (2025); Muchiri et al. (2020)
6	Insufficient Resources and Time Pressure	Organizational	Overload and resource scarcity constrain creative exploration and experimentation.	Sjahrudin et al. (2024); Ebrahim et al. (2023)
7	Low Psychological Safety	Team / Organizational	Fear of judgment or criticism discourages idea sharing and open communication.	Mozie & Mahadi (2024); Ajrurrahman & Pusparini (2024)
8	Weak Empowering Climate	Organizational	Limited autonomy and lack of participative decision-making reduce innovative engagement.	Al-Qahtani (2025); Chakim et al. (2024)
9	Technological and Environmental Uncertainty	Contextual	Rapid technological change and market turbulence create uncertainty in innovation outcomes.	Chakim et al. (2024); Khan (2021)
10	Cultural Barriers and Lack of Collaboration	Organizational / Team	Poor communication, weak work structures and weak team dynamics inhibit knowledge sharing.	Manalo et al. (2025); Ajrurrahman & Pusparini (2024)

3.5. Conceptual Framework

The review reveals that fostering IWB in NPD projects can be achieved through a complex interplay of antecedents, mediating and moderating

mechanisms, outcomes and barriers. These can be conceptually framed as give in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework - Innovative Work Behavior

4. Discussion

4.1. Synthesis of Findings

The interpretation and the combination of the results from this SLR leads to a comprehensive, multi-level portrait of IWB as a central concept in current organizational research and shows that IWB is not a one-of-a-kind phenomenon, but a dynamic behavioral process that is influenced by antecedents, mediators, moderators, contextual barriers and outcomes. At antecedent level, both individual and organizational level factors are also seen to be key enablers in which leadership constructs like transformational leadership, entrepreneurial and ethical leadership is seen to be a critical enabler that provides the encouragement to the employee to be creative, autonomous and recognize the opportunity in challenges. Also, organizational enablers such as support, climates, human resource management, knowledge sharing cultures and psychological empowerment are seen to foster a fertile condition for innovative behavior manifestation which seems to conclude that the social cognitive process jointly influence the innovation oriented behavior. At the mediating level, psychological and behavioral mechanisms are key to the translation of enabling

conditions into innovation outcomes, whereas psychological empowerment, self-efficacy, agility as employee and creativity are consistently important mediators explaining leadership and climate stimulating IWB. Thus, innovation is identified as primarily the function of internalized motivation and confidence which is bolstered by external systems of support. Moderators (such as empowering climate, work involvement, organizational justice and proactive personality further specify these relationships by suggesting when and for whom, IWB will work and by suggesting that personal interaction and organizational justice matter for the intensity of innovative responses. On the other hand, the synthesis identifies several barriers that limit innovation, such as fear of failure, low self-efficacy and scarcity, indicating that the barriers are beyond individual control and need to be overcome, like for instance, by fostering a culture of psychological safety, managerial support and adaptive learning mitigates resistance to change. Outcomes of IWB are multidimensional, namely individual growth, team effectiveness, organizational performance, etc., IWB

supports adaptability, competitiveness, sustainability, by turning the creative potential into something tangible and thus showing the value of IWB is that IWB can be understood as a behavioral capability system sustained by empowering leadership, mediated by psychological factors, moderated by contextual enablers and hindered by structural barriers. Therefore, promoting IWB requires a holistic organizational strategy which will have leadership, culture and individual development integrated to transform creativity into sustained innovation.

4.2. Theoretical Contributions

This research contributes to the theoretical literature of IWB. It suggests a multi-level model that combines leadership, psychology and organizational behavioral concepts, demonstrating how these individual/relational and situational factors interact to form IWB. Synthesizing findings from 2000 to 2025, it expands theories like SCT and demonstrates that the influence of leadership on innovative performance depends on employees' empowerment, self-efficacy, and agility (Ebrahim et al., 2023 and Chakim et al., 2024). The study proposes the concept of entrepreneurial leadership as a unique antecedent and provides an original insight into opportunity-driven innovation in dynamic environments. It also identifies empowering climate and work involvement are key moderators. Finally, by combining both constraints and drivers in a single model the study offers a comprehensive picture of innovation behavior as a motivational and situational system that is embedded in leadership, culture and psychological mechanisms. This synthesis closed the research gap and positioned IWB as a behavioral capability system that relies upon supporting leadership and empowering environments. The framework clears the blurring of the lines between individual agency and organizational context, which in turn indicates that IWB can mutually support leadership practices. Furthermore, the model accounts for cross-cultural differences by and large through moderating the strength of psychological mediators by condition contextual variables, thus providing a flexible framework for future empirical studies.

4.3. Practical Implications

The study provides empirical recommendations for managers and policymakers who want to foster IWB in project based organizations. It emphasizes on leadership development that establishes entrepreneurial and transformational qualities that will create IWB and foster creativity and risk taking among leaders and employees (Mozie & Mahadi, 2024). An empowering climate, participative decision making and open communication that encourages employees to try explore without worrying about failure. Also, HR practitioners can support IWB from a strategic HRM perspective with ongoing learning and recognition systems and provide flexibility in work practices that will increase psychological empowerment and agility (Jishnu & Hareendrakumar, 2024). Organizations should also foster knowledge sharing cultures and cross-functional collaboration. Organizations should also facilitate individual creativity growth to collective innovative growth. At the individual level, self-efficacy and psychological capital-building interventions through mentoring, coaching and innovation workshops thus helping workers overcome resistance to change. Performance metrics and reward systems should be rewarding creative efforts. Also, instead of short term efficiency, these should be matching incentives and innovation goals. Finally, this paper emphasizes the fact that innovation is a result of conducive systems with adaptive leadership and psychologically safe environments that together unleash the potential of employees and promote continuous innovative performance. Additionally, the integration of inventive tasks in organizational procedures and the career model being linked to creative occupational purposes enhances the everlasting commitment. Suggesting for practitioners that the climate and leadership practices should be constantly checked for suitability and if necessary, changed to maintain an environment to experiment.

4.4. Limitations and Future Recommendations

Several shortcomings have been recognized in this synthesis. Firstly, it will only be based on peer-reviewed publications between 2000-2025, which may inevitably miss findings and local contexts especially those of the developing countries. Secondly, the qualitative methodologies used in the majority of the included studies are cross-sectional and therefore, are

less able to infer causal relationships between antecedents and outcomes. Dynamic development of IWB is captured by long-term studies including multiple sources. Third, the distinction between leadership and climate has dominated the literature, with organizational structure, digital transformation and socio-cultural moderators are insufficiently taken into consideration. Changes in work patterns need to be captured in future research investigating technology mediated innovation, artificial intelligence driven collaboration and remote working environments. Testing of the integrated framework across diverse cultural and industry settings specially in emerging economies like Pakistan it would improve generalization of the studies. Finally, a more balanced understanding of IWB can be obtained by looking in depth at the negative or dark-side factors (innovation fatigue, idea rejection or idea overload). Filling these gaps will enhance theoretical precision and provide applied knowledge to organizations on how to deal with the delicate interface of potential and performance in innovation. Furthermore, through qualitative case studies, finer mechanisms of IWB which may be overlooked by the quantitative survey could be revealed. The incorporation of mixed-methods using triangulation would also improve the likelihood of confidence in the proposed relationships. Finally, the understanding of the impact of policy-level interventions can provide guidance to governmental agencies of the innovation ecosystem creation regarding IWB.

5. Conclusion

Innovative work behavior is conceptualized as a staged, behavioral process through which employees explore opportunities, generate ideas, advocate them and realize them and as such contribute towards organizational performance and competitive advantage. Research finds a complex interplay of individual variables (personality traits, psychological empowerment, self-efficacy and others), leadership variables (mainly transformational and ethical leadership) and organizational variables (culture, climate, HR practices and knowledge transfer mechanisms) to affect IWB. Leadership will create supportive climates, psychological safety and fairness conditions, which will positively influence motivation and capacity to innovate, whereas an innovation

climate, cooperation, and incentives will further promote IWB. Despite this knowledge there are gaps in understanding how these determinants interact and how some HR practices impact on IWB. Therefore, integrative longitudinal studies are required to develop rigor in such research. Although the literature has provided empirical evidence that IWB is related to firm performance across industries, and it serves as a micro foundation for organizational innovation, the theoretical causal pathways and mediating variables need further robust, multi-level research. Existing integrated frameworks incorporate behavioral stages, antecedents and outcomes, but they are not empirically validated and do not consider new phenomena such as digital leadership and generational differences. Future work will need to create a unifying taxonomy, examine the sustainment of IWB over time, sector specific dynamics and new leadership styles and organizational systems that promote new work behaviors that will support IWB as a strategic asset in a rapidly changing competitive environment.

REFERENCES

- Ajrurrahman, A., & Pusparini, E. S. (2024). The influence of transformational leadership and organizational justice on innovative work behavior: The mediating role of psychological capital and knowledge sharing. *Ekombis Review : Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi dan Bisnis*, 12(4). <https://doi.org/10.37676/ekombis.v12i4.6605>
- AlEssa, H. S., & Durugbo, C. (2021). Systematic review of innovative work behavior concepts and contributions. *Management Review Quarterly, Springer*, vol. 72(4), pages 1171-1208, December. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11301-021-00224-X>
- Alfy, S. E., & Naithani, P. (2021). Institutional and employee antecedents of innovative work behavior: A systematic review. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*, 13(4), 377–396.
- Almeida, L., & Moreira, A. (2022). Workplace innovation: A search for its determinants through a systematic literature review. *Business: Theory and Practice*, 23(2), 502–524. <https://doi.org/10.3846/btp.2022.14928>
- Al-Qahtani, K. M. (2025). The impact of innovation-oriented organizational climate on employee's creative behavior: A case study in Poland. *المجلة*

- العربية، 8(1).
<https://doi.org/10.21608/aja.2025.346276.1768>
- Booth, A., Sutton, A., & Papaioannou, D. (2023). Systematic approaches to a successful literature review (3rd ed.). Sage.
- Braun, D., & Follert, F. (2024). Agility and innovative behavior in digital product development teams. *Technovation*, 131, 102659.
- Chakim, M. H. R., Utami, R. T., Sitanggang, T. W., Tanjung, A., Rizky, A., & Beldiq, E. A. (2024). Innovation behavior research: Global trends and emerging themes in entrepreneurial business practices. *Aptisi Transactions on Technopreneurship (ATT)*, 6(3).
<https://doi.org/10.34306/att.v6i3.476>
- Dayanti, P. R. (2024). Innovative work behavior on millennial and generation-z: A literature review. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies*, 7(3), 251-257.
<https://doi.org/10.51386/25815946/ijms-v7i3p114>
- Delhi, K. (2024). Leadership climate for innovation: The moderating role of trust and collaboration. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 45(2), 245-263.
- Donthu, N., Kumar, S., & Pattnaik, D. (2021). How to conduct a systematic literature review: A guide for management scholars. *Journal of Business Research*, 133, 285-299.
- Ebrahim, Z. B., Ismail, I., & Kassim, E. S. (2023). A conceptual review of the determinants of employee innovative work behavior. *Information Management and Business Review*.
[https://doi.org/10.22610/imbr.v15i4\(si\).i.3598](https://doi.org/10.22610/imbr.v15i4(si).i.3598)
- Hai, T. T. T., Lan, M. T., & Ngoc, L. T. M. (2024). The relationship between work environment and employees' innovative work behaviours: A proposed model. *VNU University of Economics and Business*. 4. 10.57110/vnu-jeb.v4i2.268.
- Handiman, R., & Adam, P. (2024). Innovative behavior and knowledge exchange in cross-functional NPD teams. *Project Leadership and Society*, 5, 100241.
- Hoon, C. (2013). Meta-Synthesis of Qualitative Case Studies: An Approach to Theory Building: An Approach to Theory Building. *Organizational Research Methods*, 16(4), 522-556. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428113484969>
- Jain, R. (2015). Psychological empowerment and innovative behavior: A study of service sector employees. *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 50(3), 471-486.
- Jishnu, A., & Hareendrakumar, V. R. (2024). Impact of HR Practices on Innovative Work Behaviour: The Mediating Role of Organizational Support, Knowledge-sharing and Employee Creativity. *Paradigm: A Management Research Journal*, 28(1), 101-118.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/09718907241251410>
- Khalili, A., & Arya, N. (2023). Innovative work behavior: Integrating creativity and implementation perspectives. *European Management Journal*, 41(2), 210-226.
- Khan, S. (2021). Exploring the firm's influential determinants pertinent to workplace innovation. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 19(1), 272-280.
[https://doi.org/10.21511/PPM.19\(1\).2021.23](https://doi.org/10.21511/PPM.19(1).2021.23)
- Kraus, S., Breier, M., & Dutta, D. (2022). Systematic literature reviews in management research: A practical guide. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 24(2), 102-127.
- Liang, J., Farh, C. I., & Farh, J. L. (2022). Psychological safety and innovative work behavior revisited. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 43(1), 24-45.
- Liu, H., Wang, X., & Zhang, T. (2023). Innovative work behavior and employee well-being: A meta-analytic review. *Human Resource Management Review*, 33(1), 100908.
- Manalo, H. D., Manalo, M. R. T., & Bibangco, E. J. P. (2025). Exploring Innovative Work Behavior to Bridge the Fragmented Knowledge. *Journal of Management World*, 2025(1), 457-466.
<https://doi.org/10.53935/jomw.v2024i4.714>
- Morales, Y. X. C., & Pacheco, O. E. C. (2024). Determinants of innovative behavior from the perspective of individual factors: A conceptual framework. *Intangible Capital*.
<https://doi.org/10.3926/ic.2389>
- Mozie, N. M., & Mahadi, N. (2024). Fostering innovative work behavior: Ethical leadership,

- psychological safety, and proactive personality. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business & Social Sciences*.
<https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v14-i8/22286>
- Muchiri, M., McMurray, A., Nkhoma, M., & Pham, H. (2020). Mapping antecedents of innovative work behavior: A conceptual review. *Journal of Developing Areas*, 54(4), 33–40.
<https://doi.org/10.1353/JDA.2020.0047>
- Mursaleen, F., Iqbal, Z., & Fatima, S. (2024). Transformational leadership and employee engagement: Implications for innovation. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 18(2), 188–205.
- Nguyen, G. T., Ly, H. T. M., Nguyen, T. H., & Hoang, S. D. (2024). Innovation leadership and workplace innovative behaviour: An experimental investigation of leadership dynamics among IT engineers in Vietnam. *International Journal of Innovation Management*.
<https://doi.org/10.1142/s1363919624500221>
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., & Bossuyt, P. M. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for systematic reviews. *BMJ*, 372, n71.
- Petticrew, M., & Roberts, H. (2006). *Systematic reviews in the social sciences: A practical guide*. Blackwell.
- Salsabila, N., & Mansyur, R. (2024). Employee creativity as a driver of innovative behavior in project teams. *Creativity Studies*, 17(2), 203–220.
- Sjahrudin, H., Abdullah, R., & Rahman, M. (2024). Innovation behavior and organizational sustainability in emerging markets. *Sustainability*, 16(5), 2419.
- Ulfat, S., Moazzam, A., & Salman, Y. (2022). Organizational innovation management: Traces from previous literature. *Global Social Sciences Review*, VII(II), 355–371.
[https://doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2022\(vii-ii\).36](https://doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2022(vii-ii).36)
- Waheed, K. Z., & Khan, M. I. (2025). Fostering Innovative Work Behavior in New Product Development Projects: A Theoretical Review. *Pakistan Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 13(2), 479–495.
<https://doi.org/10.52131/pjhss.2025.v13i2.288>
- Yang, S., & Park, J. (2023). Knowledge sharing and empowerment as mediators of leadership–innovation links. *International Journal of Project Management*, 41(6), 819–833.
- Yasir, M., Irshad, M., & Khan, M. (2022). Transformational leadership and innovative work behavior: A review and research agenda. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 16(1), 45–61.
- Yuwanda, T., Gustina, L., & Bella, S. (2023). Increasing Competitive Advantage Through Creativity and Innovative Behavior: The Moderating Role of Digital Leadership. *MIX: Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen*, 13(1), 63-77..

